

Arab International University
Faculty of Business Administration

**The Impact of Digital Marketing on the Organization's
Operational Efficiency
Case Study of Warco Petrolum MOBIL1 Company**

Prepared by:

Nawar Al-Shwike

Haya Al-Kayal

Supervised by:

Dr. Arig AlKhatib

Dr. Lilas Allahham

2025-2026

Acknowledgement

هيا:

الى امي:

أنتِ قدوتي في الحياة، وبكِ تعلمت معنى الصبر والقوة والعطاء.
كان دعاؤك سرّ نجاحي، وكان دعمك سبب تفوقي.
هذا الإنجاز لكِ قبل أن يكون لي، فلكِ الفضل في كل ما وصلتُ إليه.

الى اخي:

وجودك في حياتي قوة، ودعمك سرّ من أسرار نجاحي. وجودك في حياتي يملأ قلبي فرحاً.

الى أبي:

شكراً لكل لحظة دعمتني فيها، ولكل كلمة رفعت من معنوياتي
وجودك في حياتي مصدر قوة وسعادة.

الى ستيفاني:

التي كانت لي أخت،
رفيقة الضحك واللحظات الصعبة،
أنتِ دائماً سندي في كل المواقف،
أشكرك على وجودك دائماً بجانبني.

الى سارة:

أنتِ الهدوء الذي يسبق الفوضى، والصديقة التي يكفي حضورها ليصبح كل شيء أسهل.
وجودك قيمة لا يُقاس بالكلام.

الى سحر:

إلى من كانت دائماً قريبة من القلب،
إلى من فهمتني من دون أن أتكلم، ووقفت بجانبني حين احتجت السند.

الى شام، كريم، جولي، حمزة:
الذين شاركوني أجمل اللحظات والذكريات، كنتم سنداً وضحكاً
وجودكم في حياتي جعل الرحلة أجمل.

الى أنس، مناف، صافي:

الذين شاركوني اللحظات الممتعة والتحديات، كنتم دائماً سنداً ورفقة تملأ الحياة طاقة
أشكركم على كل دعم ومرح قدمتموه لي.

الى ليان، ليا، تالا، جودي، المي:

الذين كانوا لي رفقة ودعمًا طوال هذه الرحلة،
شاركتموني التحديات والضحك والسهرات الطويلة،
وجودكم بجانبني جعل تجربتي الجامعية أغنى وأجمل.

الى بيرو، نجوى، جهان، جلنار، يانا:

الذين يملؤون حياتي بالحب والفرح،
محبتكم في قلبي مكانها دائم ولا تنسى أبدًا.

نوار:

أبي:

سندي الأول وقوتي، الذي علّمني معنى الإصرار والمسؤولية، وكان دعمه وإيمانه بي دافعاً للاستمرار وتجاوز الصعوبات.

أمي:

نبع الحنان والصبر، التي أحاطتني بدعائها ومحبتها في كل مرحلة، وكانت دائماً الملجأ الآمن ومصدر الطمأنينة عند التعب.
أهدي لكما هذا الإنجاز المتواضع، فهو ثمرة تعبكما وتضحياتكما، وامتداد لكل ما غرستموه في من قيم ومحبة.

أخي الدكتور عبد المجيد:

الذي كان حاضراً في كل مرحلة، قريباً بتوجيهه ودعمه، ومتابعاً لتفاصيل هذا الطريق خطوة بخطوة. وجوده الدائم وإيمانه بي كانا مصدر قوة حقيقي.

أخي الدكتور سارية:

الذي لم يبخل أبداً بتشجيعه ونصائحه، ووجوده الدائم إلى جانبي كان مصدر راحة وثقة طوال هذه الرحلة.

شريكة الدرب عليا:

التي كانت أكثر من مجرد رفيقة طريق، سنداً روحياً وعملياً في أدق التفاصيل وأصعب المراحل. حضورها الدائم، وكلماتها المشجعة، وإيمانها بي جعلوا الرحلة أخف وأكثر ثباتاً.

دكاترتي، وبالأخص الدكتورة أريج والدكتورة ليلاس:

خالص الشكر لأساتذتي الكرام على علمهم وتوجيههم. وأخص بالشكر الدكتورة أريج والدكتورة ليلاس على دعمهم الذي أحدث فرقاً حقيقياً في مسيرتي.

حمزة وغيث وحسام ومعاذ واسامة:

الشكر على وقفهم الصادقة طوال حياتي الجامعية كانوا العون الذي لا يُقدّر بثمن.

ماهر وطارق:

الى طارق، الذي كان حاضرًا دائمًا في كل خطوة من خطواتي، يشاركني التحديات والنجاحات، ويقف إلى جانبي في كل لحظة صعبة أو فرحة، وجوده جعل الطريق أخف وأجمل.

إلى ماهر، صديق الطفولة الذي عرفني منذ زمن بعيد ورافقني بوفائه ودعمه، أهديكما هذا الإنجاز عرفانًا لكل لحظة صدق ووفاء رافقتني منذ الصغر.

يوسف، أمير، علي، وجميع أصدقائي المقربين:

جميعكم قدمتموا لي المحبة والدعم. كنتم جزءًا أصيلاً من هذا الإنجاز وتشجيعكم المستمر.... ممنونٌ لكونكم بجانبني.

زملائي في الجامعة:

تشاركنا الدرب ودرسنا سوية

تشاركنا الفرح والتعب والسهر. شكرا لوجودكن بجانبني طول هذه السنين.

ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of digital marketing on operational efficiency, using Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company as a case study within the Syrian market. In an era of rapid digital transformation, organizations increasingly rely on digital marketing tools not only to enhance customer engagement but also to improve internal operational performance. The research aims to explore how digital marketing strategies (especially social media platforms and company websites) contribute to cost reduction and resource optimization.

The study adopts a mixed-methods research approach, combining qualitative data collected through in-depth interviews with company managers and quantitative financial analysis based on key operational efficiency indicators. Qualitative findings reveal that digital marketing plays a vital role in strengthening market presence and enhancing coordination between marketing, sales, and customer service functions. Quantitative analysis further demonstrates strong operational performance, reflected in low customer acquisition costs, high client lifetime value, favorable operating expense ratios, and a high operating margin.

The results indicate that digital marketing significantly contributes to operational efficiency by lowering marketing costs, improving asset utilization, and enabling real-time performance monitoring. The study concludes that digital marketing should be viewed not merely as a promotional tool, but as a strategic component of operational management.

Table of Contents

Title	Page
Title Page	1
Acknowledgment	2
Abstract	6
Chapter one: Conceptual Framework	8
1.1 Introduction	8
1.2 Literature Review	9
1.3 Comment on Literature Review	16
1.4 Research Problem	17
1.5 Research Significance	17
1.6 Research Objectives	18
1.7 Research Questions	18
1.8 Research Methodology	19
1.9 Research Terms	20
Chapter two: Theoretical Background	21
2.1 Digital Marketing	21
2.2 Operational Efficiency	41
Chapter three: Practical chapter	50
3.1 Company Profile	50
3.2 Data Collection	52
3.3 Financial Analysis	53
3.4 Results	63
3.5 Recommendations and Suggestions	66
Conclusion	68
References	69

Chapter one: conceptual framework

- **Introduction:**

In today's era, organizations are increasingly changing digital marketing strategies not only to attract and retain customers but also to enhance their internal operations. Digital marketing tools such as data analytics, automation platforms, and real-time communication channels have transformed how businesses interact with their audiences and manage their resources. These technologies enable organizations to optimize workflows, reduce operational costs, and improve overall productivity. This research aims to explore the extent to which digital marketing contributes to operational efficiency within organizations. By analyzing the integration between marketing functions and operational processes, the study seeks to uncover how digital strategies can optimize performance, support decision making, and drive growth.

- **Literature Review:**
 1. **Study of (Ali et al., 2025, Pakistan) Titled “Impact of Digital Transformation on SME’s Marketing Performance”:** The study aims to explore social media’s role in marketing agility which was measured using structural equation modeling. The study sample included (250) SMEs. The study findings were enhanced responsiveness, asset efficiency, and profit margins.
 2. **Study of (Al-Qahtani, 2024, GCC countries) Titled “Digital Transformation and Operational Efficiency in GCC Service Firms”:** The study aims to assess the impact of digital customer experience on operational and financial efficiency in service firms which was measured using surveys to evaluate digital channel usage for customer experience. The study sample included service firms in GCC countries. The study findings were that enhanced digital customer experience was positively linked to improvements in operating profit margin and return on sales (ROS).
 3. **Study of (Sharabati et al., 2024, Jordan) Titled “The Impact of Digital Marketing on the Performance of SME’s”:** The study aimed to analyze how digital marketing affects SME performance, which was measured using Quantitative survey as well as regression analysis. Where the study sample was (300) SME’s. The study findings were improved customer acquisition, reduced costs, enhanced net profit margin and operational efficiency.

- 4. Study of (Brighton Nyagadza, Eugene Tafadzwa Maziriri, 2023, South Africa) Titled “Digital Marketing and Its Impact on Business Performance: A Case Study of Retail SMEs in South Africa”:** The study aims to evaluate how digital marketing strategies affect operational efficiency and financial performance in retail SMEs which was measured using quantitative surveys. The study sample included (210) retail SMEs across Johannesburg and Cape Town. The study findings were that digital marketing significantly improved inventory turnover, customer engagement, and cost efficiency.
- 5. Study of (Gohar et al., 2023, Pakistan) Titled “Market Turbulence and Digital Marketing Agility”:** The study aims to study how digital marketing helps firms adapt to market volatility which was measured using structural equation modeling. The study sample included (200) SMEs. The study findings were that digital tools improve adaptability, responsiveness, and profitability.
- 6. Study of (Zhang & Chen, 2023, China) Titled “ The Impact of Digital Marketing Capability on Firm Performance”:** The study aims to examine how digital marketing capabilities effect financial performance in industrial firms which was measured using quantitative surveys to assess five elements of digital capability maturity. The study sample included industrial firms in China. The study findings were that digital capabilities were positively associated with return on assets (ROA) and operating profit margin.

7. Study of (Ayorinde, 2023, Finland) Titled “The Impact of Digital Marketing on SME Profitability and Performance”:

The study aimed to examine post-COVID digital marketing impact on SME profitability which was measured using mixed-method (interviews+ surveys). The study sample included SME's in Finland. The study findings were reduced fixed costs, improved targeting, and better asset utilization.

8. Study of (Jilcha, 2023, Ethiopia) Titled “The Effects of Digital Marketing on Business Performance: The Case of Ethio Telecom”: The study aims to assess digital tools' impact of telecom performance which was measured using quantitative analysis. The study sample included (200) employees. The study findings were improved engagement and operational efficiency.

9. Study of (Hidayat et al., 2022, Indonesia) Titled “The Impact of Digital Marketing: A Systematic Literature Review”: The study aimed to review digital marketing strategies and outcomes which was measured using systematic literature review of (45) studies. Where the study sample was on a global scope. The study findings were enhanced engagement, better targeting, improved profitability and responsiveness.

10. Study of (Amin et al., 2022, Malaysia) Titled “Digital Marketing and Firm Performance: Evidence from Emerging Markets”: The study aims to examine digital marketing’s effect on financial performance which was measured using regression analysis. The sample study included (300) SME’s. The study findings were increased ROI and better resource allocation.

11. Study of (Wisdom Apedo Deku, Jiuhe Wang, & Alexander Kofi Preko, 2022, Ghana) Titled “ Digital Marketing Strategies and Their Impact on Business Performance” : The study aims to investigate how digital marketing strategies affect SME performance, including operational efficiency and profitability which was measured using quantitative analysis using structured questionnaires and regression modeling. The study sample included (178) SMEs across various sectors in Ghana. The study findings were social media marketing improved operational responsiveness, while website optimization enhanced customer conversion and asset utilization.

12. Study of (Kumar et al., 2022, India) Titled “Digital Marketing’s Impact on Asset Productivity in Manufacturing”: The study aims to assess digital marketing’s effect on asset productivity which was measured using regression and KPI tracking. The study sample included (250) manufacturing firms. The study findings were improved

machine utilization and profit margins through digital engagement.

13. Study of (Li & Zhao, 2022, China) Titled “Digital Transformation Capability and Operational Efficiency”: The study aims to investigate the relationship between digital marketing transformation and operational efficiency which was measured using quantitative indicators and a structured survey. The study sample included firms undergoing digital transformation in China. The study findings were that digital transformation efforts improved operating expense ratio and asset turnover, indicating enhanced operational efficiency.

14. Study of (Pop et al., 2022, Romania) Titled “ Digital Marketing and SME Competitiveness in Romania”:

The study aims to examine digital marketing’s role in SME competitiveness which was measured using survey and performance metrics. The study sample included (150) SMEs. The study findings were enhanced visibility, better cost control, and improved margins.

15. Study of (Alalwan et al., 2021, Jordan) Titled “Social Media and Its Connection to Business Performance”: The study aims to investigate social media’s influence on business performance which was measured using survey-based SEM. The study sample was (400) SMEs. The study findings were positive impact on customer retention and operational agility.

16. Study of (El-Haddad & Ben Youssef, 2021, MENA Region) Titled “Digital Marketing Adoption and Financial Efficiency in SMEs”: The study aims to assess the impact of adopting digital marketing tools on financial efficiency in small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) which was measured using surveys to measure adoption levels of tools like email marketing, SEO, social media, and websites, plus digital spending data. The study sample included SMEs in MENA Region. The study findings were that high adoption of digital tools led to a reduction in the cost-to-revenue ratio and an increase in operating profit margin.

17. Study of (McKinsey & Company, 2021, Global) Titled “ How Digital Marketing Operations Can Transform Business”: The study aims to evaluate how the maturity of digital marketing operations affects business performance which was measured using internal benchmarking using a 0-100 scale based on (20) operational and marketing KPIs. The study sample included global firms across sectors. The study findings were that higher digital maturity is correlated with lower operating expenses and improved profit margins.

18. Study of (Roland Rust, Valarie Zeithaml & Katherine Lemon, 2020, USA) Titled “Driving Customer Equity: How Customer Lifetime Value Is Reshaping Corporate Strategy”:

The study aims to link customer equity and digital marketing to financial performance which was measured using longitudinal analysis. The sample study included (100) firms across industries. The study findings were digital engagement improves customer lifetime value and net profit margin.

19. Study of (Kumar & Peterson, 2020, United States) Titled “The Role of Analytics in Improving Marketing Efficiency”:

The study aims to explore how digital analytics improve marketing and financial efficiency which was measured using quantitative analysis using performance metrics such as customer acquisition cost (CAC) and customer lifetime value (CLV). The study sample included U.S. based firms using advanced analysis platforms. The study findings were that the use of digital analytics significantly reduced CAC and improved the CLV/CAC ratio, enhancing financial operational efficiency.

20. Study of (Don Peppers & Martha Rogers, 2018, USA) Titled “The One-to-One Future”:

The study aims to analyze personalized digital marketing’s effect on operations which was measured using case-based analysis. The study sample included retail and telecom firms. The study findings were one-to-one marketing improves efficiency and asset utilization.

- **Comment of Literature Review:**

The reviewed literature has many common themes with the current study. Most importantly, prior research consistently highlights the positive impact of digital marketing tools such as the website, and social media platforms on various aspects of organizational performance.

However, this research differs from previous studies in several key ways. Unlike most prior research that treats digital marketing as a driver of external performance, this study emphasizes its role in internal operational efficiency such as asset utilization and the net profit margin. Finally, by focusing on the Syrian market, this research addresses a geographic and economic context that remains underrepresented in existing literature, providing fresh insights into digital transformation in emerging economies.

- **Research Problem:**

In light of rapid digital transformation, organizations are increasingly relying on digital marketing tools to enhance customer engagement and strengthen their market presence. However, it remains unclear to what extent it contributes to improving internal operational efficiency such as reducing costs and enhancing internal coordination. The research problem stems from the need to understand the relationship between the implementation of digital marketing strategies and the effectiveness of operational performance, particularly in business environments

facing economic and technological challenges. Especially for emerging and newly established companies like Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company, which recently opened a branch in Syria, it was essential to identify the most suitable digital marketing strategies that would help it improve its profitability, competitiveness, and operational efficiency under the current technological and economic conditions in the country.

- **Research significance:**
- **Academic Significance**
- It contributes to the growing body of literature on digital marketing by linking it to internal operational outcomes.
- The study offers a theoretical framework that integrates marketing and operations.

- **Managerial Significance**
- The findings will provide decision-makers in Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company with insights into how digital marketing tools can be used to improve workflow efficiency, reduce operational costs, and enhance resource utilization.
- It supports strategic planning by identifying which digital strategies submit the greatest operational benefits, helping managers in Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company align marketing efforts with performance goals.

- **Research objective:**

A study basically aimed to examine the impact of digital marketing on operational efficiency in Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company. This aim is supported by the following objectives:

- To examine the relationship between digital marketing practices and operational efficiency within Petroleum MOBIL1 Company.
- To identify which digital marketing tools and strategies contribute most significantly to improving internal workflows, resource utilization, and cost reduction of Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company.
- Estimate how digital marketing could improve the operational efficiency of Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company.
- To provide practical recommendations for integrating digital marketing strategies into operational planning to enhance overall Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company performance.

- **Research questions:**

The main question this study wants to answer is:

How digital marketing impacted the operational efficiency of Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company?

This question is supported by the following question:

- What digital marketing strategies were used in Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company?
- What measures of Operational Efficiency were used in Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company?

- What measures of digital marketing were used in Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company?
- How is Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company applying digital marketing strategies to enhance and improve operational efficiency?
- **Research Methodology:**

This study will adopt a mixed methods research technique, according to (Saunders & et.al, 2023). **Mixed methods research** designs integrate the use of quantitative and qualitative data collection procedures and analysis techniques in the same research project. Its designs may use deductive, inductive approaches to theory development. (Saunders & et.al, 2023, 187).

The suitability of this method for the study is that it is a case study of a Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 company. Because it's one of the Principal associated research designs to case study strategy (Saunders & et.al, 2023, 191).

A case study is an in-depth inquiry into a topic or phenomenon within its real-life setting (Yin 2018). Where it has the capacity to generate insights from intensive and in-depth research into the study of a phenomenon in its real-life context, leading to rich, empirical descriptions and the development of theory (Yin 2018). They can be designed to identify what is happening and why, and to understand the effects of the situation and implications for action; often using both qualitative and quantitative data from a range of sources. (Saunders & et.al, 2023, 206).

An orthodox case study strategy involves an approach that is rigorously defined and highly structured before the research commences, with the intention that it will proceed in a linear way. This reflects the rational approach to conducting research where literature is reviewed first, the research question is defined, the research project is designed, preparation for the conduct of the research undertaken, and data are

collected, analyzed, interpreted and then reported. (Saunders & et.al, 2023, 208).

Case study research often uses a combination of archival records and documents, different forms of observation, interviews and focus groups, questionnaires, reflection and the use of research diaries and other research aids. (Saunders & et.al, 2023, 208).

Accordingly, in this study we will collect qualitative data through interviews with managers in Warco Petrolum MOBIL1 and analyze it qualitatively, and collect financial data from documents and interviews and analyze it quantitatively.

- **Research Terms:**
- Digital Marketing: The use of digital channels to promote products or services and engage with customers.
- Operational Efficiency: The ability of an organization to deliver services in the most cost-effective way while maintaining quality.

Chapter two: Theoretical Background

2.1. Digital Marketing:

2.1.1. Definition of digital marketing:

Digital marketing uses technology intensive platforms such as the internet, mobile networks and devices, and social media to engage directly with individual consumers, consumer communities, and businesses. It uses these platforms to provide information, build engagement, persuade consumers, induce brand purchase, and ultimately drive profitable transactions and long-term relationships. (Kotler P, 2024, 518).

Digital marketing can be simply defined as: Achieving marketing objectives through applying digital media, data and technology.

This succinct definition helps remind us that it is the results delivered by technology that should determine investment in digital marketing, not the adoption of the technology, we also need to remember that despite the popularity of digital devices for product selection, entertainment and work, we still spend a lot of time in the real world, so integration with traditional media remains important in many sectors.

In practice, digital marketing focuses on managing different forms of online company presence, such as company websites, mobile apps and social media company pages (Chaffey D, Chadwick F, 2022, 38) .

Digital marketing is essential to the Pashmina industry because it helps

companies advertise to more people, increase sales, and retain existing clients. As increased consumers become familiar with the Pashmina brand and its goods, digital marketing has become essential to the industry. According to a study by (Ghimire and Gurung, 2019, CH2), Brand recognition, more sales, and devoted customers are all achievable goals for Pashmina companies with the aid of digital marketing. Pashmina firms may set themselves apart from the competition and win over more clients by promoting themselves via digital channels like social media, search engine optimization, and email marketing (Ghimire & Gurung, 2019, 542).

2.1.2. Benefits of Digital Marketing:

Its rapid growth reflects the fact that digital marketing offers many benefits to both buyers and sellers. Its major benefits are summarized in this section.

- **Buyer Benefits:**

For buyers, digital marketing is convenient, easy, and private. It gives buyers anywhere, anytime, and personalized access to an almost unlimited assortment of goods and a wealth of product and buying information. For example, on its website and mobile app, Amazon.com offers more information than most consumers can digest, ranging from continually updated top 10 product lists, extensive product descriptions, and expert and user product reviews to recommendations based on consumers' previous searches and purchases. Also, buyers can customize products and information they want, order on the spot, and

receive delivery within days or even hours.

- **Seller Benefits:**

Digital marketing also offers sellers multiple benefits. First, digital marketing can provide an efficient alternative for reaching markets. While large companies are embracing digital marketing, this benefit is especially important for new or small companies that might otherwise be locked out of established channels and stores. For example, artists who handcraft unique goods can market them to the world on Etsy.com. Likewise, small independent companies can sell through and even establish their own storefronts on Amazon.com. With software and support from online store developers like Shopify, small companies can sell through their own websites, establishing a brand and customer base before creating a brick-and-mortar presence.

Digital marketing gives marketers the flexibility to dynamically adjust information, prices, and offerings to create timely and personalized customer engagement and value. And companies can set up online forums to enhance customer engagement and service (Kotler P, 2024, 520).

2.1.3. The 7Ds of digital marketing:

As part of defining the scope of opportunity when using a strategic approach to digital marketing, it's helpful to think about which digital audience interactions we need to understand and manage through marketing communications. Digital marketing today is about managing many more types of audience interaction than simply a company

website or email marketing. It involves harnessing all of these other “7Ds of managing digital marketing interactions”. The 7Ds that should be reviewed as part of a strategic approach to digital marketing are:

- **Digital goals and strategies:** Reviewing what the business or brand is aiming to achieve through using digital marketing and how well it is contributing. Considering how digital marketing can help the business compete through digital marketing strategy to define digital transformation needed for existing businesses, including changes to business and revenue models, and prioritization of always-on marketing in addition to campaign investments.
- **Digital audiences:** Understanding online audience characteristics, behaviors and preferences, summarized as personas, in order to deliver more relevant content and experiences to different target segments, aimed at increasing interactions and so meeting business goals within the competitive online marketplace.
- **Digital devices:** Understanding how our audiences interact with businesses as part of the buying process using a combination of smartphones, tablets, laptops, desktop computers, TVs, gaming devices, smart speakers and other connected devices forming the Internet.
- **Digital platforms:** Assessing the relative importance of interactions and priority for communications on the major ‘digital platforms’ or online services, sometimes described by the acronym ‘FAMGA’. These businesses are influential in developing the operating systems, browsers, apps, social networks and search engines used to

mediate digital interactions between businesses and consumers. Industry sectors may have their own platforms that are important in influencing purchase, for example specialist online publishers or comparison sites. For example, within the travel sector, TripAdvisor™ is an important platform, built using the infrastructure provided by different FAMGA players.

- **Digital media:** Prioritizing the use of different communications channels for reaching and engaging audiences that are available, including advertising, email and messaging, search engines and social networks, which we'll introduce in this chapter.
- **Digital data:** Structuring and applying the insight businesses collect about their audience profiles; their interactions with businesses now need to be protected by law in most countries.
- **Digital marketing technology:** Selecting the marketing technology or martech that is used to create interactive experiences including websites and mobile apps. Technology is also used to support the planning, execution, optimization, insight and reporting for digital marketing channel activities that form marketing campaigns (Chaffey D, Chadwick F, 2022, 36).

2.1.4. Digital Marketing Strategies:

Digital marketing refers to advertising a product or service through digital channels, including social media platforms. A Digital Marketing Agency is responsible for enhancing our brand's online visibility.

Digital marketing strategies encompass diverse digital channels to

advertise products and services, enhance brand recognition, and stimulate sales. Presented below are a few instances of digital marketing strategies, and we will focus on both social media and website in this research

- **Search Engine Marketing (SEM) :**

SEM, also known as search engine marketing, is a highly effective approach to expanding our business in an increasingly competitive market. Word-Stream is a prominent provider of SEM solutions.

- **Email Marketing:**

Email marketing refers to sending focused emails to customers and subscribers to promote goods and services. One can accomplish this objective by crafting customized content, categorizing email lists, and implementing automated campaigns.

According to a study by (HubSpot, 2021), Email marketing boasts a high return on investment, effectively cultivates leads and fosters customer loyalty (Hubspot, 2021).

- **Content Marketing:**

According to a study by Content Marketing Institute (2021), Implementing content marketing strategies can enhance brand recognition, lead generation, and business sales growth (Content Marketing Institute, 2021.311). To effectively capture and retain the attention of potential customers, content marketing necessitates the creation of top-notch materials, including blog posts, videos, and infographics.

- **Mobile Advertising:**

As per the report published on the Datar portal, the total number of cell phone users in Nepal has reached 42.78 million as of early 2023, which accounts for approximately 139.2% of the total population. Likewise, this indicates that there are sixteen million internet users, highlighting a significant potential for mobile advertising in our nation (Data Report, 2023, 22).

- **Website Marketing:**

- **Definition of Website Marketing:**

The company's website is the crucial point of its digital marketing campaigns and is a medium for customer engagement. The purpose of the website is to facilitate collaboration and foster genuine dialogue. Websites derive their corporate influence from their capacity to present product and company information, often catalogs, as evidence of the company's identity and central communication (Kotter, 2014, 201). Additionally, it serves as a means of collecting customer data for evaluation and measurement. This data is utilized to attract potential customers, convert leads into clients, guide consumers through purchasing, and maintain communication with clients for post-sale service. (INDRA BAHADUR BASNET, 2022, 23).

- **Brand Community Websites:**

As a first step in online marketing, most companies create a website. Websites vary in purpose and content. Some websites are primarily marketing websites, designed to engage customers and move them

closer to a direct purchase or other marketing outcome. For example, SHEIN, a Chinese fast fashion retailer, operates an online fashion store.

Once a potential customer clicks in, SHEIN wastes no time offering various discounts and coupons to convince them to buy their products. The site provides all the information needed for a successful transaction: clothes are available in different sizes up to 4XL, delivery is free of charge above a certain amount, and buyers can choose from several different categories. In contrast, brand community websites primarily aim not to sell products but to present brand content that engages consumers and creates customer–brand communities. Such sites offer a rich variety of brand information, videos, blogs, activities, and other features (Kotler P, 2024, 525).

A company's website in effect is an advertisement for the company. However, beyond being a form of advertising, websites represent a venue for generating and transacting exchanges between organizations and their customers. Websites can be considered the centerpiece of companies' online advertising efforts, with other advertising formats (e.g., paid searches, streaming video, e-mail) simply serving to drive traffic to their websites. Affiliated or sponsored sites are also an option for some marketers. On the affiliate site there.com (www.there.com), visitors can create their own avatar and interact with brands such as Scion, Coca-Cola, SPIN, and Cosmo. (Andrews J & Shimp T (2018), 13-5)

- **Site design and structure:**

The structures created by designers for websites will vary greatly according to their audience and the site's purpose, but we can make some general observations about common approaches to site design and structure and their influence on consumers. These are often known as 'best-practice principles of website design' and in this section we will summarize some of the main factors. Of course, there are exceptions to such rules of thumb or 'heuristics', but often a design approach that works on one type of site will work on another, particularly if it is a common feature across the majority of sites. (Rosen and Purinton, 2004, 65).

Assessed the design factors that influence a consumer (based on questionnaires completed by a group of students). They believe there are some basic factors that determine the effectiveness of an e-commerce site.

They group these factors as follows:

- **Coherence:** simplicity of design, easy to read, use of categories (for browsing products or topics), absence of information overload, adequate font size, uncrowded presentation.
- **Complexity:** different categories of text.
- **Legibility:** use of 'mini home page' on every subsequent page, same menu on every page, site map.

Devising a site that is easy to use is critically dependent on the design of the site navigation scheme. Hoffman and Novak (1997) and many subsequent studies (e.g. Rettie, 2001; Smith and

Sivakumar, 2004, 59) have stressed the importance of the concept of flow in governing site usability.

It can be suggested that there are three important aspects within a site or app that is easy to navigate. These are:

- **Consistency.** A site will be easier to navigate if the user is presented with a consistent user interface when viewing the different parts of the site. For example, if the menu options in the support section of the site are on the left side of the screen, then they should also be on the left when the user moves to the ‘news section’ of the site.
- **Simplicity.** Sites are easier to navigate if there are a limited number of options.

It is usually suggested that two or possibly three levels of menu are the most that are desirable. For example, there may be main menu options at the left of the screen that take the user to the different parts of the site, and at the bottom of the screen there will be specific menu options that refer to that part of the site (menus in this form are often referred to as ‘nested’).

- **Context.** Context is the use of ‘signposts’ to indicate to users where they are located within the site – in other words, to reassure users that they are not ‘lost’. To help with this, the website designer should use particular text or color to indicate to users which part of the site they are currently using (Chaffey D, Chadwick F, 2022, 346).

- **Website performance optimization:**

It's important for site owners to recognize that page download performance is essential to the success of a site, even when many users have broadband connections and sites are hosted with high-bandwidth connections to the internet.

Site performance has become more important with the increased adoption of smartphones, which typically have lower bandwidth connections than desktops. Research by (Google, Karnowski, 2017) has shown that the recommended average user perception of acceptable download time is two seconds, while for the average European website it is around eight seconds. To encourage businesses to improve site performance, Google has created tools such as Page Speed Insights to provide benchmarking data and identify bottlenecks restricting performance. (Google (2021) noted that longer page load times have a severe effect on bounce rates (which measure the proportion of visitors to a page who stay on the page/site or leave).

- If page load time increases from 1 second to 3 seconds, bounce rate increases 32 per cent.
- If page load time increases from 1 second to 6 seconds, bounce rate increases by 106 per cent. (Chaffey D, Chadwick F, 2022, 296-298).

Google (2021) also explains why new Core Web Vitals measures were introduced for webmasters to review their page performance in Google Search Console, which should be monitored for every business, since poor experience for users may be penalized in organic search engine

rankings.

Search engine optimization is one of the broadest and most complex areas of marketing. It can be enormously frustrating and enormously rewarding.

Much like social media, the goals can often be muddled and the techniques for delivering against those goals a little mysterious.

To excel in this field, you need to have a scientific understanding of code and technology, a creative understanding of content, a good PR head to generate meaningful links and an all-round skillset in project management.

That's a tough ask for any single person and so building a team or working with consultants or an agency is often the right solution. However, you cannot lead that agency unless you at least have a grounding in the core areas.

There are many considerations in SEO. You are surrounded by a lot of jargon and a lot of acronyms. This is simply because there are so many levers to pull from coding changes to content frequency. Before we get into the tactical implementation, we are going to look at the foundations. These are the things you must understand and act upon at the very start³¹ (Kingsnorth, Simon (2022, 311)).

- **Social Media Marketing:**
- **Definition of Media Marketing:**

The surge in internet usage and digital devices has spawned an array of social media. People now congregate to socialize and share messages, opinions, pictures, videos, and other content on numerous independent and commercial social networks.

Millions of people worldwide are buddying up on Facebook, checking in with Twitter tuning to the day's hottest videos on YouTube, pinning images on Pinterest, or sharing photos and videos on

Instagram, Snapchat, and TikTok. And, of course, wherever consumers congregate, marketers will follow.

Marketers are now riding the social media wave. Large brands usually have a sprawling social media presence. For example, according to one source, Nike maintains at least 108 Facebook pages, 104 Twitter handles, 16 Instagram accounts, and 41 YouTube channels. Interestingly, even as marketers are mastering the use of social media, social media platforms are adapting to better support marketers. These parallel efforts benefit both social media users and brands. (Kotler P, 2024, 528).

Social media have been defined as '[incorporating] the on-line technology and methods through which people can share content, personal opinions, swap different perspectives and insights, using text, images, audio and visual (Dibb *et al.*, 2012). The advent and

popularity of such websites has meant many things for marketers (McDaniel *et al.*, 2013):

- Marketers often no longer control content relating to their brands.
- The ability to share experiences takes word of mouth to a whole new level.
- Social media allow us to listen to (or ignore!) customer complaints more easily.
- Social media are mobile so we can communicate while customers are on the move.
- Social media facilitate a more direct and meaningful dialogue with customers than has previously been possible.

Social networking has developed very quickly and is still in a period of rapid change. Marketers are unsure as to how to make the most of such sites for their corporate benefit, and many organizations are supplementing their marketing departments with social media experts. (Alan Tapp, 2014, 295).

- **Types and Functions of Social Media:**

Marketers must first understand the functional capabilities of different social media platforms. They can then integrate an effective combination of these platforms into their digital marketing strategies.

Here we review just some of a broad array of social media platforms and discuss how marketers can employ them:

- **Image and Video Platforms:** Companies can use platforms such as Flickr, Instagram, TikTok, and Snapchat to manage visual storytelling, introduce new products, create brand personalities, and collect customers' ideas.
- **Messaging Platforms:** Companies can work with messaging platforms such as WhatsApp, Kik, and China's WeChat to engage directly with consumers. For instance, Mobike has a WeChat mini-program that helps users locate, unlock, and pay for shared bikes.
- **Blogs/Microblogs:** With its 280-character limit, Twitter is, at its heart, a hyper-efficient blog. Many companies are moving away from issuing staid press releases and instead embracing Twitter as a favored medium for rapidly disseminating brand and company news and tackling customer complaints. As noted previously, most companies also operate one or more blogs.
- **Wikis:** Wikis are collaborative knowledge networks that are created and managed by the public. Wikipedia is one of the world's greatest sources of knowledge. Individuals and companies can contribute to knowledge on Wikipedia. Johnson & Johnson's Wikipedia entry, for example, helps build the corporate brand by providing an in-depth exploration of the company's history, values and heritage, products and services, and high and low points across time. Other wikis are more focused.
- **Reviews and Ratings Platforms:** Today, consumers rate their experiences on many platforms. Yelp offers crowdsourced consumer reviews and ratings of everything from local restaurants

and auto service providers to plumbers, dentists, and barbers. Consumers rate their experience on a five-star scale and can provide a written review.

- **Social media objectives:**

As with all marketing, social media needs to have clear objectives set so that its success can be measured and evaluated.

Some of the followings are suggested (McDaniel *et al.*, 2013) when drawing up such media objectives:

- **Sell:** Social media are increasingly generating sales.
- **Listen and learn:** Monitor what is being said about the brand and its competitors and glean insights about audiences. Use on-line tools and do research to implement the best social media practices.
- **Develop new channels to market:** social media provide unique and credible new routes to market. They allow for interaction and dialogue to and between customers and the companies that serve them.
- **Build relationships and awareness:** Open dialogues with stakeholders by giving them compelling content across a variety of media. Engage in conversations and answer questions candidly. This will both increase Web traffic and boost your search engine ranking.

- **Promote products and services:** The clearest path to increasing the bottom line using social media is to get customers talking about products and services, which ultimately translates to sales. Creating a buzz about your products and services and using the ability of social media to share content can allow messages to ‘go viral’ with both positive and potentially negative consequences.
- **Manage your reputation:** Develop and improve the brand’s reputation by responding to comments and criticisms that appear on blogs and forums. Position yourself as helpful and benevolent by participating in other forums and discussions. Social media make it much easier to establish and communicate expertise. Look at how companies engage with review sites. Trip Advisor has some influence in the travel market. Jury’s Inn has an excellent approach to the monitoring of, and engagement in, this channel, quickly dealing with negative postings and thanking customers for their positive comments.
- **Improve customer service:** Customer comments about products and services will not always be positive.
- Use social media to find displeased customers and engage them directly to solve their service issues (Alan Tapp, 2014, 295).

- **Social Media Advantages and Disadvantages:**

Using social media presents both advantages and challenges. On the plus side, social media allow marketers to share targeted and personalized brand content with consumers and communities. Social

media are interactive, enabling companies participate in consumer conversations and collect feedback. Social media are also immediate and timely (Chaffey D, Chadwick F, 2022, 443).

They can reach customers anytime, anywhere with timely and relevant marketing content and interactions.

Social media can be cost-effective. Although creating social media content can be expensive, many social media platforms are free or inexpensive to use. Thus, returns on social media investments are often higher than those on TV and print media. Even small businesses with skimpy marketing budgets can use social media.

Perhaps the biggest advantage of social media is their engagement and social sharing capabilities (Kotler P, 2024, 533).

As a relatively new set of options for advertisers and consumers, social media (e.g., social networking, blogging, wikis, collaboration, virtual worlds) has had its share of ever-evolving advantages and disadvantages.

- **Advantages include:**
- **Flexibility:** The use of social media offers tremendous flexibility in marketing and advertising planning, with the ability to quickly modify apps, postings, ads, and blogs in response to competitive and industry changes.
- **Reach options:** Increased targeting via behavior, demographics, site visits, and posted preferences and likes has helped with the ability of advertisers to reach small audiences with social media. At the same time, the scale of some social networking sites (e.g.,

Facebook, Twitter) allows advertisers to reach extremely large audiences as well.

- **Consumer engagement:** With consumer-generated content, it helps to ensure engagement in sites such as YouTube, Flickr, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat, Pinterest, etc., as well as brands and companies featured on these sites. Online panel data has long shown the link between online advertising and purchase behavior.
- **Disadvantages include:**
- **Privacy and censorship:** These issues have occurred repeatedly with social network sites, such as Facebook and Twitter. For instance, location-based apps have allowed users to tag other friends from sites for which they were never there.¹⁷ Recently, Twitter and LinkedIn allowed greater censorship of tweets in some countries than users desired.¹⁸ Google recently standardized their privacy policy and also has fought a long-running battle with Chinese authorities over censorship of content.
- **Lost productivity, addiction, and fatigue:** With an average of 25 hours per month spent by U.S. Facebook users on average, many companies worry that employees working on social media projects will experience lost productivity. In fact, there have been cases (in general) of social media addiction, burnout, or fatigue (Andrews J & Shimp T, 2018, 314).

- **Measurement of Social Media Campaigns:**

(Based on J. Craig Andrews Marquette University & Terence A. Shimp

University of South Carolina study integrated marketing communications) A survey of 1,000 online businesses indicates that companies continue to struggle with measuring the return on investment (ROI) of social media efforts.

In the survey, 41 percent of the companies report they do not have a ROI measure for any of the money spent on social media. Just 8 percent can determine the ROI of all of what they spend on social media. Part of the problem is not that there is dearth of metrics and firms—because there are many of both. Rather, the constant stream of (usually “count”) data on social media creates the “illusion of precision.” Many statistics can be gleaned directly from the social media site itself. For example, Facebook offers an EdgeRank Score that is an algorithm that Facebook uses to determine which of a page’s statuses the page’s online community will see in their news feed.¹²⁴ The algorithm is calculated as: *EdgeRank Score = Affinity × Weight × Time Decay*

The affinity score is based on the number of times that it is sends messages to a friend and check their profile; a greater number of messages and checks leads to a higher affinity score (Andrews J & Shimp T 2018,313).

2.2. Operational Efficiency:

- **Concept of Operational Efficiency:**

Operational efficiency is a critical performance metric that reflects how effectively an organization utilizes its resources to deliver products or services while minimizing waste and maximizing output. It is widely regarded as a cornerstone of sustainable business performance.

According to Santos (2016), operational efficiency involves achieving a balance between effectiveness and efficiency, where effectiveness refers to doing the right tasks and efficiency refers to doing the tasks right. Santos introduces the concepts of Absolute Operational Efficiency (AOE) and Relative Operational Efficiency (ROE), which are used to evaluate productivity across different organizational levels. These models help organizations assess how well they are converting inputs into outputs without unnecessary resource consumption.

Johnson (2015) emphasizes that operational efficiency is the ability to deliver products and services in a cost-effective manner without compromising quality. His work highlights the importance of minimizing operational waste and optimizing resource allocation. Harvard Business Review (2021) expands the concept by linking operational efficiency to digital transformation. It describes operational efficiency as the strategic alignment of resources, processes, and technologies to achieve maximum output with minimal input.

- **The Relationship Between Operational and Financial Efficiency:**

Operational efficiency refers to how effectively an organization utilizes its resources to produce goods or services with minimal waste. Financial efficiency, on the other hand, reflects in what way a firm manages its financial resources to generate profits, maintain liquidity, and ensure long-term sustainability. The relationship between these two concepts is both reciprocal and reinforcing.

According to Ndolo (2015), operational efficiency directly influences financial performance by reducing operating costs and improving profit margins. In his study of firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Ndolo found that companies with streamlined operations tended to report stronger financial outcomes. Specifically, the study concluded that “firms that improved their operational processes experienced a measurable increase in return on assets and net profit margins” (Ndolo, 2015, p.17). Atasu Journal (2021) supports this view by demonstrating that operational efficiency contributes to better capital structure management. The study used regression analysis to show that firms with higher operational efficiency had lower debt ratios and better equity utilization. This suggests that efficient operations not only reduce costs but also improve the firm’s ability to manage financial obligations and investments. Springer (2023) expands the framework by evaluating health centers in Praia City using Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). The study found a strong correlation between operational, economic, and financial efficiency. Facilities that

optimized staffing, scheduling, and resource allocation also demonstrated higher financial efficiency, measured through cost recovery and budget adherence. This reinforces the idea that operational improvements translate into financial discipline and resilience.

In summary, operational efficiency is not merely a technical or logistic concern, it is a strategic lever for financial performance. Organizations that invest in process optimization, automation, and resource alignment are more likely to achieve financial stability, profitability, and growth.

- **Dimensions of Financial Operational Efficiency:**

Financial operational efficiency is a multidimensional concept that evaluates how effectively an organization utilizes its financial and operational resources to achieve optimal performance. These dimensions can be broadly categorized into quantitative and qualitative measures, each offering unique insights into organizational health and productivity.

- **Quantitative dimensions** are numerical indicators that provide measurable evidence of efficiency. These include metrics such as cost to income ratio, return on assets (ROA), inventory turnover, operating margin, and asset utilization rates. According to Johnson (2015), these indicators are essential for benchmarking performance across time periods and against industry peers, as they allow for objective evaluation and statistical analysis (Johnson, 2015, p.2).

For example, a declining cost to income ratio may signal improved operational efficiency, while a rising ROA indicates better use of financial resources to generate profits.

- **Qualitative dimensions**, on the other hand, focus on non-numerical aspects such as employee satisfaction, customer experience, process adaptability, and organizational culture. Santos (2016) emphasizes that while these factors are harder to quantify, they play a critical role in shaping long-term efficiency outcomes by influencing innovation, service quality, and internal collaboration (Santos, 2016, p.1, second paragraph).
- For instance, a culture that encourages continuous improvement can lead to more efficient workflows and better financial performance over time.

The Department of Finance Australia (2023) highlights that a balanced performance framework should ideally include both types of measures. However, it also notes that where possible, quantitative indicators are preferred because they are more transparent, easier to track, and better suited for setting performance targets and accountability (Department of Finance, 2023, para.

- Quantitative data can be aggregated, modeled, and visualized to support decision making, whereas qualitative data often require interpretation and may introduce subjectivity.

In practice, organizations often use a combination of both. For example, a healthcare provider might track patient wait times (quantitative) alongside patient satisfaction surveys (qualitative) to assess service efficiency. However, when it comes to financial operational efficiency quantitative measures are generally favored. They provide a clear, data-driven foundation for evaluating performance, identifying inefficiencies, and justifying strategic decisions.

To conclude, while both quantitative and qualitative dimensions contribute to the understanding of financial operational efficiency, quantitative metrics are preferred in research and practice due to their objectivity and alignment with financial reporting standards.

- **Importance of Operational Efficiency**

Operational efficiency is a foundational concept in business performance, referring to the ability of an organization to deliver products or services using minimal resources while maintaining quality. Its importance lies in its direct impact on profitability, cost control, and long-term sustainability.

- One of the most critical benefits of operational efficiency is cost reduction. Bakic (2024) explains that efficient operations reduce unnecessary expenditures by streamlining workflows, automating repetitive tasks, and optimizing resource allocation. This is particularly vital in industries with tight margins, here even small improvements in efficiency can lead to significant financial gains

(Bakic, 2024, para.3).

- Operational efficiency also enhances profitability. Woods (2025) highlights that organizations that maximize output while minimizing input tend to report stronger operating margins and better overall financial performance. This is because efficient operations allow firms to scale without increasing costs, improving their return on investment (Woods, 2025, para.3).
- Another key advantage is competitive agility. As noted by CurrentWare (2025), operationally efficient firms are better equipped to respond to market changes, customer demands, and regulatory shifts. In today's digital-first and hybrid work environments, agility is a strategic asset that enables organizations to maintain relevance and resilience (CurrentWare, 2025, para.4).
- Furthermore, operational efficiency contributes to employee productivity and engagement. When processes are well-designed and resources are effectively managed, employees can focus on tasks rather than navigating inefficiencies. This leads to improved morale and better financial performance and organizational stability.
- Finally, operational efficiency is essential for sustainable growth. It enables organizations to make data-driven decisions, forecast accurately, and allocate capital effectively.

In summary, operational efficiency is indispensable for modern organizations. It drives profitability, enhances responsiveness, and strengthens internal capabilities.

- **Measuring Operational Efficiency**

Operational efficiency is best assessed through quantitative metrics that reflect how effectively an organization converts inputs into valuable outputs. Among the most widely used indicators are the Operating Expense Ratio, Customer Acquisition Cost, Return on Assets, Operating Profit Margin, Asset Utilization, and Return on Sales.

- **Operating Expense Ratio (OER):** This ratio measures the proportion of operating expenses to total revenue. A lower OER indicates higher efficiency, as it reflects the organization's ability to generate revenue while controlling costs. According to Advance IT (2025), OER is a critical benchmark for internal cost management and is especially useful in service-based industries (Advance IT, 2025, para.3).
- **Customer Acquisition Cost (CAC):** CAC calculates the average cost of acquiring a new customer, including marketing and sales expenses. NILG.AI (2025) notes that efficient operations reduce CAC by improving conversation rates and leveraging automation. A declining CAC signals improved operational and marketing alignment (NILG.AI, 2025, para.4)

- **Return on Assets (ROA):** ROA evaluates how effectively a company uses its assets to generate profit. It is calculated by dividing net income by total assets. Johnson (2015) emphasizes that high ROA reflects strong asset deployment and operational discipline, making it a key indicator of financial and operational synergy (Johnson, 2025, p.2).
- **Operating Profit Margin:** This metric shows the percentage of revenue remaining after deducting operating expenses. It reflects the core profitability of operations before interest and taxes. Woods (2025) highlights that a rising operating margin is a sign of improved efficiency, as it indicates better cost control and pricing strategy (Woods, 2025, para.3).
- **Asset Utilization:** Asset utilization measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate revenue. Santos (2016) introduces this concept within his Relative Operational Efficiency (ROE) model, showing that firms with high asset turnover tend to outperform competitors in both operational and financial terms (Santos, 2016, p.1, second paragraph).
- **Return on Sales (ROS):** ROS calculates the percentage of revenue that becomes profit after all operating costs. It is a direct measure of operational profitability. FlowGenius (2025) explains that ROS is particularly useful for comparing performance across departments, helping managers identify areas of inefficiency (FlowGenius, 2025, para.2).

- **Burn rate:** The rate at which a company depletes its cash reserves, usually measured monthly. It indicates how long a company can sustain operations before needing more funding.
- **Runway:** The number of months a company can continue operating before its cash runs out. It helps startups plan fundraising and manage costs.
- **Client value:** The overall worth of a client to a business. Identifying high-value clients helps businesses allocate resources effectively and build long-term growth.
- **Break-even point:** The sales level where total revenue equals total costs, resulting in zero profit and zero loss. It is critical for pricing, financial planning, and determining the minimum sales needed to sustain operations.

Chapter three: Practical chapter

3.1. Company Profile:

- **Basic Information**

- **Brand Name:** Mobil 1™
- **Parent Company:** ExxonMobil
- **Founded:** 1974 (launch of the first synthetic motor oil)
- **Headquarters:** United States of America
- The present study is conducted on the branch situated in Syria, in the Al-Halabouni district.
- **Industry:** Synthetic motor oils and lubricants for automotive, aviation, and industrial applications

- **Vision & Mission**

- **Vision:** To remain the global leader in advanced synthetic lubrication solutions that maximize engine performance and longevity.
- **Mission:** Deliver innovative, high-quality synthetic oils that protect engines under extreme conditions and meet the evolving needs of drivers and industries worldwide.

- **Products & Services**

- Synthetic Motor Oils: Superior protection against wear, friction, and extreme temperatures.
- Transmission Fluids and Industrial Lubricants: Designed for high-performance machinery and heavy-duty applications.
- Aviation & Specialty Lubricants: Trusted solutions for aerospace and specialized equipment.
- Motorsport Oils: Officially used in Formula 1, NASCAR, and other global racing competitions.

- **Achievements**

- Pioneer of synthetic motor oil technology since 1974.
- Long-standing partnerships with leading motorsport teams (e.g., Formula One, NASCAR).
- Proven performance: Mobil 1 oils have been tested to protect engines for over one million miles.

- **Target Market**

- Individual Drivers: Everyday car owners and high-performance vehicle enthusiasts.
- Commercial Clients: Transportation companies, aviation, and industrial sectors.
- Global Reach: Available in more than 100 countries worldwide.

- **Core Values**

- Innovation in lubrication technology.
- Reliability and superior quality.
- Commitment to sustainability and environmental responsibility.

- **Contact Information**

- Website: [Mobil 1 Official]
(<https://www.mobil.com/en/lubricants/about-us/mobil-1>)
- Parent Company: ExxonMobil

3.2 .Data collection:

Data was collected through in-depth interviews with managers of SMEs operating in the Syrian market. The interviews were designed to capture not only the perceived benefits of digital marketing but also its influence on internal processes and operational efficiency.

Managers were asked about:

- Competitive challenges in a market increasingly dominated by global players.
- The digital tools and platforms they rely on (social media, websites, email, customer service systems).
- The financial and operational impact of digital campaigns compared to traditional marketing.
- The role of digital marketing data in shaping internal coordination

and resource allocation.

This qualitative approach provided rich, experience-based insights into how integrate digital marketing into their daily operations and how it reshapes their efficiency.

3.3. Data analysis:

Thematic analysis was employed to identify recurring patterns across the interviews. Responses were grouped into four major themes:

1. Competition and Strategic Positioning – SMEs face intense competition from multinational companies, requiring digital strategies to maintain visibility and customer loyalty.
2. Digital Tools as Operational Assets – Social media and websites are not only marketing channels but also platforms for customer engagement and service management.
3. Financial Efficiency – Digital marketing reduces costs compared to traditional campaigns, improving profitability and resource utilization.
4. Operational Efficiency and Internal Coordination – Digital campaigns generate actionable data that helps adjust product focus, allocate resources more effectively, and improve collaboration between sales and marketing teams.

3.3.1. Interview Results Analysis:

- **Analysis**

1. General Questions about the Company and Context

- How would you describe the company's current position in the Syrian market?
- In your opinion, what are the main operational challenges the company is facing today?

Managers Answer: At present, competition in the Syrian market is highly intense due to the entry of major international companies. The primary challenges lie in establishing the company's presence in Syria, demonstrating its credibility, and building a strong layer of customer relationships.

2. Questions about Digital Marketing Strategies

- What are the main digital marketing tools the company relies on (website, social media, email marketing, etc.)?
- How do you evaluate the effectiveness of digital campaigns compared to traditional methods?
- Are there specific strategies that you felt delivered more tangible results than others?

Managers Answer: The most significant tools are social media platforms and the company's official website. Efforts are underway to establish a dedicated team for digital follow-up, including email communication, customer service, and online interactions. The effectiveness of these tools has been remarkable; since the initiation of social media campaigns,

sales have increased noticeably. Sponsored advertising campaigns on social media have proven particularly valuable, as they enable the company to target specific customer segments relevant to its market.

3. Questions about Operational Efficiency

- In your view, how has digital marketing helped improve internal workflows or reduce costs?
- Have you noticed changes in indicators such as customer response speed, resource utilization, or profit margins after applying digital marketing?
- How do you practically measure the impact of digital marketing on operational performance?

Managers Answer: Digital marketing has contributed to cost reduction, as traditional marketing campaigns are significantly more expensive compared to online strategies.

4. Questions about the Relationship between Digital Marketing and Operations

- Is there clear coordination between the digital marketing department and other operational departments (such as sales or customer service)?
- How have digital analytics tools supported better decision-making in operations?

- Do you see digital marketing as just a promotional tool, or has it become part of improving the company's internal efficiency?

Managers Answer: Coordination between departments is essential. For instance, when sales data indicates a decline in a specific product, marketing campaigns are directed toward that product to enhance its performance. Digital tools assist in identifying the appropriate audience for each product, thereby improving outcomes. In this way, digital marketing serves not only as a promotional tool but also as a means of enhancing internal efficiency.

- **Results**

The interviews revealed several key findings:

- **Competition:** Managers emphasized that global entrants have raised the bar, making digital presence essential for survival. Building strong customer relationships through digital channels is now a strategic necessity.
- **Digital Tools:** Social media platforms and company websites emerged as the most effective tools. Dedicated teams handle email communication, customer service, and online campaigns, integrating marketing with operational functions.
- **Sales Impact:** Paid social media campaigns significantly boosted sales by targeting specific customer segments, demonstrating the precision and effectiveness of digital tools.
- **Cost Reduction:** Compared to traditional advertising, digital

campaigns were far less expensive, allowing SMEs to achieve greater reach with lower budgets.

- Operational Efficiency: Digital marketing data enabled managers to identify underperforming products and redirect campaigns to improve their sales. This data-driven approach enhanced internal coordination and optimized resource allocation, directly improving operational efficiency.

The findings highlight that digital marketing is not merely a promotional tool but a driver of operational efficiency in digital marketing:

- Operational Resource Optimization: By leveraging customer data from digital campaigns, Company can allocate resources more strategically. For example, focusing marketing efforts on weak-performing products reduces waste and maximizes output.

- Cost Efficiency: Digital marketing provides a cost-effective alternative to traditional advertising, lowering operational expenses while maintaining or even increasing market reach. This efficiency translates into improved profitability and sustainability.

- Data-Driven Decision Making: Digital platforms generate real-time insights into customer behavior, enabling SMEs to make informed decisions about product focus, campaign timing, and audience targeting. This reduces uncertainty and enhances operational agility.

- Internal Coordination: The integration of digital marketing with

sales and customer service fosters better communication across departments. Campaigns are aligned with sales data, ensuring that marketing efforts directly support operational goals.

-Strategic Resilience: In highly competitive markets, digital marketing equips with the tools to adapt quickly, maintain relevance, and strengthen customer relationships. This resilience is crucial for sustaining operational efficiency in the face of global competition. Overall, the analysis confirms that digital marketing contributes to operational efficiency by reducing costs, improving coordination, and enabling data-driven resource management. It transforms marketing from a peripheral activity into a central component of operations.

3.3.2. Financial Analysis:

- **Presentation of Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 company's basic financial data:**

- Investor capital: 400,000
- Funding sources: The funding source is internal
- Number of employees: 21
- Fixed costs: 14,668
- Variable costs: 39,094
- First months' revenues: 39,000

- **Cost structure:**

- **Fixed costs:**

- Salaries: 4,052
- Rent: No rent
- Technical infrastructure: 4,000,000
- Licenses: 25,000 per year
- Internet and fixed services: 2,000

- **Variable costs:**
 - Digital advertising: 2,500
 - Sales commissions: 6,000
 - Shipping: 60,000
- **Calculating the basic financial indicators of a start-up:**
 - **Burn rate:** Burn rate=Total monthly expense-Total monthly revenue

$$= 57,814-39,000$$

$$= 18,814$$
 - **Runway:** Runway=Cash on hand/Burn rate

$$=70,137/18,814$$

$$= 3.7 \text{ months}$$
 - **Customer acquisition cost (CAC):** CAC=Total marketing spend/Number of new customers

$$= 7,000/34$$

$$= \$205.9$$

- **Client value (CLV):** $CLV = \text{Average purchase value} * \text{Purchase frequency} * \text{Customer lifetime}$

$$= 840 * 1.3 * 12$$

$$= \$13,104$$

- **CAC/CLV**

$$= 205.9 / 13,104$$

$$= 0.016$$

- **Operational efficiency analysis:**

- **Operating expense ratio (OER):** $OER = \text{Operating expense} / \text{Operating revenue}$

$$= 18,263 / 50,477$$

$$= 0.36$$

- **Operating margin:** $\text{Operating margin} = \text{Operating income} / \text{Revenue}$

$$= 33,540 / 39,000$$

$$= 0.86$$

- **Profit margin:** $\text{Profit margin} = \text{Net income} / \text{Total Revenue}$

$$= 11,280 / 39,000$$

$$= 0.29$$

- **Customer Profitability per year:** Customer profitability=
CLV * Profit margin
= 13,104 * 0.29
= 3,800

- **Break-even point analysis:**

Break-even units=Fixed costs-Variable cost per unit

$$=14,668-10.35$$

$$= 14,678$$

3.4. Results:

- The firm records a **burn rate** of 18,814, indicating that this amount of capital is expended per operating period to sustain ongoing activities.

- Based on current spending patterns, the firm has a financial **runway** of 3.7 months, meaning that existing capital reserves will support operations for approximately 3.7 months before being exhausted if no changes are made to cost structures.

- **The customer acquisition cost (CAC)** is 205.9, representing the average expenditure required to acquire a new customer.

- **The estimated customer lifetime value (CLV)** is 13,104, reflecting the total revenue expected to be generated from an individual customer over the duration of the business relationship.

- The resulting **CAC/CLV ratio** is 0.016, indicating that customer acquisition costs constitute only 1.6% of the value generated by each customer, which reflects a highly efficient customer acquisition strategy.

- **The operating expense ratio** is 0.36, indicating that 36% of total revenue is allocated to operating expenses.
- The **operating margin** is 0.86, suggesting that 86% of revenue remains after operating expenses, which demonstrates strong operational efficiency.
- The firm achieves a **profit margin** of 0.29, meaning that 29% of total revenue is retained as net profit.
- **Each customer generates an average annual profit** of 3,800, highlighting substantial customer-level profitability.
- Finally, the firm's **break-even point** is reached at 14,678 units sold, representing the minimum sales volume required for total revenues to equal total costs.

- **Scenario Analysis:**

Using scenario analysis is very important for startup companies. It helps founders see how changes in things like CAC, cost, or sales will impact their burn rate and runway, and how long the company can continue operating under different situations. This allows them to spot risks early, plan ahead, and make better decisions about spending and pricing before problems become critical.

	CAC	Burn Rate	Runway
Base Case	\$205.9	18,814	3.7 months
Best Case	\$164.72	15,051	4.63 months
Worst Case	\$247.08	22,577	3.08 months

Best Case: We lowered the CAC by 20% to check its effect on the burn rate and runway. The CAC fell to \$164.72. The burn rate also declines by 20%, from 18,814 to 15,051 per month. The company's runway increases from 3.7 months to 4.63 months. This gives the company an additional 0.93 months of runway.

Worst Case: We increased the CAC by 20% to check its effect on the burn rate and runway. The CAC rose to \$247.08. The burn rate also increases by 20%, from 18,814 to 22,577 per month. The company's runway decreases from 3.7 months to 3.08 months. This reduces the company's runway by 0.62 months.

3.5. Recommendation and Suggestion:

1. Enhance Digital Channels

- Email Marketing: Develop a structured email marketing program by building a customer database, sending regular newsletters, and using personalized campaigns to strengthen long-term relationships.

- Website Development: Modernize the company's website to ensure a user-friendly design, integrate live chat for customer support, and optimize for search engines (SEO) to increase visibility. Linking the website with social media platforms will further boost engagement.

2. Implement Advanced Analytics

- Adopt tools such as Google Analytics and Meta Business Suite to monitor campaign performance.

- Generate monthly reports to evaluate the impact of digital marketing on sales, costs, and customer engagement.

3. Strengthen Internal Coordination

- Establish clear communication channels between the digital marketing and sales departments.

- Share sales data regularly to identify underperforming products and direct campaigns accordingly.

- Hold weekly review meetings to adjust strategies based on

results.

4. Focus on Customer Engagement

- Launch digital loyalty programs to reward repeat customers.
- Conduct online surveys to measure customer satisfaction and gather insights for improvement.

5. Future Expansion

- Consider developing a mobile application to showcase products and facilitate orders.
- Invest in influencer marketing to build trust and reach wider audiences.
- Explore opportunities in e-commerce platforms (e.g., Amazon, Noon) to expand market reach.

Conclusion

This study confirms that digital marketing has evolved into a strategic operational function that directly influences organizational efficiency. The case of Warco Petroleum MOBIL1 Company illustrates that digital marketing contributes not only to market visibility, but also to internal cost control, resource optimization, and improved coordination between departments. The findings demonstrate that integrating digital marketing data with operational decision making allows managers to identify underperforming products, allocate resources more effectively, and respond quickly to market changes. This integration enhances operational agility and reduces unnecessary expenditures. Financial indicators further support these conclusions, showing that efficient digital marketing practices are associated with low customer acquisition costs, strong operating margins, and favorable cost structures. These results indicate that digital marketing plays a vital role in supporting sustainable profitability. In conclusion, organizations operating in competitive environments should add digital marketing to their operational strategies. Doing so enables firms to achieve higher efficiency, strengthen competitiveness, and support long-term growth.

References

- **Books:**

1- Andrews, J. C., & Shimp, T. A. (2018). *Advertising, promotion, and other aspects of integrated marketing communications* (10th ed.). Cengage Learning.

2- Chaffey, D., & Chadwick, F. E. (2022). *Digital marketing* (8th ed.). Pearson Education.

3- Dibb, S., Simkin, L., Pride, W. M., & Ferrell, O. C. (2012). *Marketing: Concepts and strategies* (6th ed.). Cengage Learning.

4- Ghimire, B., & Gurung, S. (2019). *Digital marketing*. Self-published.

5- Kingsnorth, S. (2022). *Digital marketing strategy: An integrated approach to online marketing* (3rd ed.). Kogan Page Publishers.

6- Kotler, P. (2014). *Principles of marketing* (Global ed.). Pearson Education.

7- Kotler, P. (2024). *Principles of marketing* (10th ed.). Pearson Education.

8- Peppers, D., & Rogers, M. (2018). *The one-to-one future: Building relationships one customer at a time* (Reprint ed.). Currency Doubleday.

9- Rosen, M., & Purinton, E. (2004). *Website design: Viewing the web as a cognitive landscape*. Journal of Business Research. Elsevier.

10- Rust, R. T., Zeithaml, V. A., & Lemon, K. N. (2020). *Driving*

customer equity: *How customer lifetime value is reshaping corporate strategy* (2nd ed.). Wiley.

11- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2023). *Research methods for business students* (9th ed.). Pearson Education Limited.

12- Tapp, A. (2014). *Principles of direct, database and digital marketing* (5th ed.). Pearson Education.

- **Researches:**

1- Alalwan, A. A., Rana, N. P., Dwivedi, Y. K., & Algharabat, R. (2021). Social media in marketing: A review and analysis of the existing literature. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(7), 1177–1190.

2- Ali, M., Khan, R., & Hussain, S. (2025). Impact of digital transformation on SME's marketing performance: Role of social media and market turbulence. *Sustainability*, 6(1), 1–15.

3- Al-Qahtani, M. (2024). Digital transformation and operational efficiency in GCC service firms. *Asian Journal of Business Research*, 14(1), 88–104.

4- Amin, M., Thurasamy, R., & Aldakhil, A. M. (2022). Digital marketing and firm performance: Evidence from emerging markets. *Journal of Business Research*, 145, 45–58.

5- Atasu Journal. (2021). Impact of operational efficiency and financial performance on capital structure. *Atasu Journal*, 6, 1–15.

Ayorinde, I. (2023). The impact of digital marketing on SME profitability and performance. [Theseus.fi](https://theses.fi).

6- Bakic, L. (2024). What is operational efficiency? [Productive.io](https://productive.io) Blog.

7- Basent, I. B. (2022). Impact of digital marketing on organizational performance.

8- Chaffey, D., & Chadwick, F. E. (2022). *Digital marketing* (8th

ed.). Pearson Education.

9- Content Marketing Institute. (2021). Marketing strategies report.

10- CurrentWare. (2025). Operational efficiency: A comprehensive guide for 2026. CurrentWare Blog.

11- Deku, W. A., Wang, J., & Preko, A. K. (2022). Digital marketing strategies and their impact on business performance: Evidence from SMEs in Ghana. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 16(3), 251–270.

12- Department of Finance. (2023). Qualitative & quantitative performance measures. Australian Government.

13- El-Haddad, & Ben Youssef, A. (2021). Digital marketing adoption and financial efficiency in SMEs: Evidence from MENA. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 70(9), 2451–2470.

14- FlowGenius. (2025). 7 key operational efficiency metrics to track in 2025. FlowGenius Blog.

15- Ghimire, B., & Gurung, S. (2019). Digital marketing. Self-published.

16- Gohar, A., Khan, M., & Raza, S. (2023). Market turbulence and digital marketing agility: Evidence from Pakistani SMEs. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 31(1), 55–72.

17- Harvard Business Review. (2021). Operational efficiency in the digital age. *Harvard Business Review*, March Issue, 2–5.

18- Hidayat, R., Prasetyo, A., & Nugroho, S. (2022). The impact of digital marketing: A systematic literature review. ResearchGate.

19- Hoffman, D. L., & Novak, T. P. (1997). Marketing study.

20- HubSpot. (2021). Email marketing report.

21- Jilcha, M. (2023). The effects of digital marketing on business performance: The case of Ethio Telecom. [Academia.edu](https://www.academia.edu).

22-Johnson, A. (2015). Operational efficiency. ResearchGate.

- 23- Karnowski, V. (2017). Google research study.
- 24-Kumar, R., Singh, A., & Patel, S. (2022). Digital marketing's impact on asset productivity in Indian manufacturing SMEs. *Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing*, 37(6), 1125–1140.
- 25- Kumar, V., & Peterson, A. (2020). The role of analytics in improving marketing efficiency. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, 8(2), 67–79.
- 26-Li, X., & Zhao, H. (2022). Digital transformation capability and operational efficiency: Evidence from Chinese firms. *Journal of Business Research*, 145, 123–135.
- 27-McKinsey & Company. (2021). How digital marketing operations can transform business. McKinsey Insights.
- 28- Ndolo, J. M. (2015). The relationship between operational efficiency and financial performance on firms listed at the Nairobi Securities Exchange. University of Nairobi Repository, 17–20.
- 29- [NILG.AI](#). (2025). Master operational efficiency metrics to boost your business. [NILG.AI](#) Blog.
- 30- Nyagadza, B., & Maziriri, E. T. (2023). Digital marketing and its impact on business performance: A case study of retail SMEs in South Africa. *Journal of Digital Marketing & E-Commerce Strategies*, 5(2), 45–62.
- 31- Pop, R., Ionescu, A., & Georgescu, M. (2022). Digital marketing and SME competitiveness in Romania: A quantitative approach. *Management and Marketing*, 17(2), 123–138.
- 32- Rettie, E. G. (2001). Digital communication study.
- 33- Santos, G. (2016). Operational efficiency. [Academia.edu](#).
- 34- Sharabati, A., Al-Hyari, K., & Al-Saqqa, I. (2024). The impact of digital marketing on the performance of SMEs. *Sustainability*, 16(19), 8667.
- 35- Smith, M., & Sivakumar, K. (2004). Study on marketing

dynamics.

36- Springer. (2023). Relationship between operational, economic, and financial efficiencies in health centers. In *Advances in Health Management*, 1–20.

37- Woods, B. (2025). Operational efficiency: Strategies and key metrics to improve. [Ninety.io](#) Blog.

38- Zhang, Y., & Chen, L. (2023). The impact of digital marketing capability on firm performance. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 9(1),12.

Appendix A – Interview Questions:

1. General Questions about the Company and Context

- How would you describe the company's current position in the Syrian market?
- In your opinion, what are the main operational challenges the company is facing today?

2. Questions about Digital Marketing Strategies

- What are the main digital marketing tools the company relies on (website, social media, email marketing, etc.)?
- How do you evaluate the effectiveness of digital campaigns compared to traditional methods?
- Are there specific strategies that you felt delivered more tangible results than others?

3. Questions about Operational Efficiency

- In your view, how has digital marketing helped improve internal workflows or reduce costs?
- Have you noticed changes in indicators such as customer response speed, resource utilization, or profit margins after applying digital marketing?
- How do you practically measure the impact of digital marketing on operational performance?

4. Questions about the Relationship between Digital Marketing and Operations

- Is there clear coordination between the digital marketing department and other operational departments (such as sales or customer service)?
- How have digital analytics tools supported better decision-making in operations?
- Do you see digital marketing as just a promotional tool, or has it become part of improving the company's internal efficiency?

